

NEW TRENDS :USE OF TOBACCO IN BIO- PHARMACEUTICALS

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Nicotiana tabacum, or cultivated tobacco, is an annually-grown herbaceous plant. It is found only in cultivation, where it is the most commonly grown of all plants in the *Nicotiana* genus, and its leaves are commercially grown in many countries to be processed into tobacco.

Tobacco is the fourth most common risk factor for disease worldwide. The economic costs of tobacco use are equally devastating. In addition to the high public health costs of treating tobacco-caused diseases, tobacco kills people at the height of their productivity, depriving families of breadwinners and nations of a healthy workforce. Tobacco users are also less productive while they are alive due to increased sickness.

A 1994 report estimated that the use of tobacco resulted in an annual global net loss of US\$ 200 thousand million, a third of this loss being in developing countries. Tobacco and poverty are inextricably linked. Many studies have shown that in the poorest households in some low-income countries as much as 10% of total household expenditure is on tobacco. This means that these families have less money to spend on basic items such as food, education and health care. In addition to its direct health effects, tobacco leads to malnutrition, increased health care costs and premature death.

The WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control, which was adopted in May 2003 by WHO's 192 member States, is intended as a common framework in which countries can work together to address the challenge that tobacco use represents at the global level. In the year 2004 the Central Govt of India passed a legislation on advertisement, production, trade and sale of tobacco and tobacco products .banning the advertisement of tobacco & tobacco products on tv, newspapers and media from 01 may 2004 Reason tobacco leaves contain an alkaloid nicotine which is lethal carcinogen and causes addiction.

Table 1 TOXIC LEVELS OF NICOTINE

A] Minimum Lethal Dose of Nicotine

- Adult Human 40 mg ~0.5- 1.0 mg/kg ;**
- **Topically Child 4mg /kg , Adult 65mg**
 - **Human 0.36mg/kg**
 - **Cow [1- 1 ½ year old Bulls & Heifer] > 1 gm**
 - **Horse & Cow 200-400 mg**
 - **Sheep 100-200 mg**
 - **18 month Lambs 200-300 mg**
 - **Cat & Dog 20-100 mg**
 - **Mouse 40 mg**

A] INDOOR AIR POLLUTION LEVELS OF NICOTINE

- Billiard parlour 19.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$
- Home 12.1- 14.4
- Departmental store 0.6
- Automobile 0.4

B] INDOOR AIR QUALITY Nicotine $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$

- Restaurants 0.5- 37 average 5.4
- 7.1 -37 average 15
- Offices 3- 48
- 9-32
- 6-20 average 5
- Public common areas 2-36
- 1-3
- Smoking sections of airplanes 6-29 average 15
- 0-112 average 9
- Non smoking sections of airplanes 0-40 average 6
- Food counters of shopping malls 1.6- 3.1 average 2.3

TABLE 4 VARIOUS BRANDS OF CHEWING TOBACCO MANUFACTURED IN INDIA [0.3-0.5 mg / gm NICOTINE CONTENT]

MAHARASTRA

- . [A3] OM SPECIAL
- [B3] HATHI CHAP

UTTAR PRADESH

- [A1] MOHINI
- [B1] SWAGAT
- [C1] SHRIRAM
- [C2] GHAI CHAP
- [C6] GANESH
- [B6] UDTA PANCHI
- [B7] HIRAN CHAP
- [B8] MEHAK
- [B9] TULSI

- [C5] MADHU

• TABLE 5 VARIOUS BRANDS OF CHEWING
TOBACCO MANUFACTURED IN INDIA

[0.3-0.5 mg / gm NICOTINE CONTENT]

JHARKHAND

[A4] RAJA CHAP

[C4] KUBER TOBACCO

[B4] MIRAJ TOBACCO

CHATISGARH

[A3] TOTA CHAP

[C3] MAHARAJA CHAP

[B5] BHARAT CHAP TEJ TOBACCO

Tobacco smoke contains over 4000 chemicals in the form of particles and gases.

Many potentially toxic gases are present in higher concentrations in sidestream smoke than in mainstream smoke and nearly 85% of the smoke in a room results from sidestream smoke.

The particulate phase includes tar (itself composed of many chemicals), nicotine, benzene and benzo(a)pyrene. The gas phase includes carbon monoxide, ammonia, dimethylnitrosamine, formaldehyde, hydrogen cyanide and acrolein. Some of these have marked irritant properties and some 60 are known or suspected carcinogens (cancer causing substances). The Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) in the USA has classified environmental tobacco smoke as a class A (known human) carcinogen along with asbestos, arsenic, benzene and radon gas [Lee Jong-wook, WHO 2004]

TOBACCO USE IN AYURVEDIC MEDICINE

- Tobacco that was made into a syrup with honey was used to treat asthma, chest diseases, cough, and syphilis
- Medicinally it is used as a sedative, diuretic, expectorant, discutient, and sialagogue, and internally only as an emetic, when all other emetics fail. The smoke injected into the rectum or the leaf rolled into a suppository has been beneficial in strangulated hernia, also for obstinate constipation, due to spasm of the bowels, also for retention of urine, spasmodic urethral stricture, hysterical convulsions, worms, and in spasms caused by lead, for croup, and inflammation of the peritoneum, to produce evacuation of the bowels, moderating reaction and dispelling tympanitis, and also in tetanus.
- To inject the smoke it should be blown into milk and injected, for croup and spasms of the rima glottides it is made into a plaster with Scotch snuff and lard and applied to throat and breast, and has proved very effectual.
- A cataplasm of the leaves may be used as an ointment for cutaneous diseases. The leaves in combination with the leaves of belladonna or stramonium make an excellent application for obstinate ulcers, painful tremors and spasmodic affections.

- Tobacco is a product prepared from the leaves of the tobacco plant by curing them. The plant is part of the genus *Nicotiana* and of the Solanaceae (nightshade) family. While more than 70 species of tobacco are known, the chief commercial crop is *N. tabacum*. The more potent variant *N. rustica* is also used around the world. Tobacco contains the alkaloid nicotine, which is a stimulant. Dried tobacco leaves are mainly used for smoking in cigarettes, cigars, pipe tobacco, and flavored shisha tobacco. They can be also consumed as snuff, chewing tobacco, and dipping tobacco. Burning tobacco is the main source of indoor pollution in the developed world. Tobacco smoke contains about 4,000 chemicals including carcinogens, irritants and toxic gases. Nicotine, benzene and benzo(a)pyrene. The gas phase includes carbon monoxide, ammonia, dimethylnitrosamine, formaldehyde, hydrogen cyanide and acrolein. Methyl bromide, an ozone-depleting chemical commonly used to fumigate the soil prior planting tobacco seedlings. Tobacco growers are susceptible to an occupational illness known as green tobacco sickness. Apart from this the Tobacco plant has multiple uses in medicine.

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- A wet Tobacco leaf applied to piles is a certain cure. The inspissated juice cures facial neuralgia if rubbed along the tracks of the affected nerve. The quantity of the injection must never exceed a scruple to begin with; half a drachm has been known to produce amaurosis and other eye affections, deafness,

TOBACCO USE IN BIO-PHARMACEUTICALS

- Ebola, is a viral hemorrhagic fever of humans and other primates caused by ebolaviruses. Signs and symptoms typically start between two days and three weeks after contracting the virus with a fever, sore throat, muscular pain, and headaches. Then, vomiting, diarrhea and rash usually follow, along with decreased function of the liver and kidneys. At this time some people begin to bleed both internally and externally. Ebola virus disease (formerly known as Ebola haemorrhagic fever) is a severe, often fatal but preventable disease. WHO declared Ebola Virus Disease as a public health emergency of international concern, under the International Health Regulations, IHR (2005) on 8 August 2014.

- ZMapp is manufactured in the tobacco plant *Nicotiana benthamiana* in the bioproduction process known as "pharming" by Kentucky BioProcessing, a subsidiary of Reynolds American. Kentucky BioProcessing in Owensboro was one of the first biopharmaceutical companies tasked with developing the ZMapp serum through tobacco plants. The company has been working in collaboration with San Diego-based Mapp Biopharmaceutical, which developed the ZMapp vaccine,
- The process involves growing tobacco plants, not in the acres of fields earmarked by tobacco companies for their cigarettes, but in a controlled environment in a greenhouse, for six weeks. Then, the leaves of the plants are injected or infused with a plant bacterium that carries a valuable payload — the genes for the antibodies that can bind to and neutralize the Ebola virus. The plant cells treat the new genes as one of their own, and start making the antibody. It takes about 14g of these antibodies to treat a patient, says Yuri Gleba, CEO of Icon Genetics, the German company that pioneered the platform, and to produce that much requires around 78 tobacco plants and about seven to 10 days.

- Drugs and vaccines are manufactured in a variety of ways. Flu vaccines, for example, are most commonly produced by injecting fertilized hen eggs with the virus. The virus is incubated for days so it can replicate, be harvested, inactivated or weakened, and then made into either a flu shot or nasal spray. The process can cost around \$150 million each year, using \$600,000 eggs each day. Tobacco plants can produce antibodies in much less time for a fraction of the cost, advocates say. The process begins by cloning a gene and inserting it into a virus. That infected gene is then injected into the tobacco plant, where it multiplies within the leaves before it is extracted and purified.

- Unlike with egg-based and mammalian cell-based products, each tobacco plant can produce enough antibodies for dozens of doses. The plants are also easy to contain and manufacture in controlled environments such as greenhouses. Medicago Inc., a biopharmaceutical company in North Carolina, produced 10 million flu vaccines in 30 days using tobacco plants in a federally funded effort called "Blue Angel." The program tested the prospect of rapid vaccine production in the hypothetical case of a global health pandemic. It is estimated the company could make as many as 100 million doses for as little as \$36 million.
- The Canadian biopharmaceutical company PlantForm is using tobacco to produce a drug that reduces the growth rate of breast cancer tumors. The drug is a "biosimilar" form of a current drug on the market called Herceptin, usually produced by creating antibodies in mammalian cells from hamsters' ovaries. The current treatment costs up to \$100,000 per patient, according to PlantForm. The company estimates up to \$120 million could be saved by 2017 by manufacturing the drug with tobacco plants instead.
- The London scientists, led by Anthony Jevnikar, chief scientific officer of London-based Plantigen Inc, a team that combined medical and agricultural researchers, modified tobacco plants to produce the human protein interleukin-10, known to reduce inflammation in humans. Fed to mice with an inflammatory disease, interleukin-10 reduced the severity of the inflammation and improved the health of the mice.
- The northwestern city of Xian is using the counterfeit cigarettes to extract solanesol, a compound found in tobacco which is used to treat cardiovascular disease.

- Tobacco will now be used for manufacturing cancer and cardiac drugs with the Central Tobacco Research Institute (CTRI) bagging the patent for 'solanesol' -- a medicinal substance extracted from tobacco.
- Solanesol, a white crystalline powder derived from tobacco's green leaf, has curative effects against cardiac insufficiency, muscular dystrophy, anaemia, cancer, diabetes, high blood pressure, asthma and liver injury. "Many pharmaceutical companies have approached us for carrying out clinical trials for the usage of solanesol as anti-cancer and anti-diabetic drugs," CTRI Director V Krishna Murthy told PTI.
- Solanesol is rich in Coenzyme Q10 -- a physiologically active substance with high pharmaceutical value. "Solanesol has excellent prospects in future as drug and CTRI would soon distribute the rights for production of drugs in the market," Murthy said. A letter granting the patent for solanesol was received by CTRI in October last year from Controller of Patents.
- The project of deriving solanesol from tobacco was a collaborative programme between CTRI and Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI), Lucknow. CTRI used chewing tobacco variety Abirmani grown in Tamil Nadu and HDBRG tobacco cultivated in black soils of Guntur in Andhra Pradesh for extracting solanesol

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TOBACCO KILLS

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